

THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY-BASED LEARNING ON THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT, PHYSICAL, AND EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING OF COLLEGE STUDENTS OF SAINT FERDINAND COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of technology-based learning (TBL) on the academic engagement, physical well-being, and emotional well-being of college students at Saint Ferdinand College, City of Ilagan. With the growing use of technology in education, this research highlights its potential benefits and challenges. Utilizing a descriptive research design, the study employed a survey questionnaire administered to 257 students across two departments. The data revealed that TBL positively influences students' academic engagement in terms of behavioral, social, and cognitive aspects, with students reporting greater satisfaction, collaboration, and motivation in learning. However, the study also identifies some negative impacts on students' physical health, such as headaches and back pain from prolonged screen use. Emotional well-being, though affected by stress and fidgetiness, showed minimal negative outcomes. Notably, students from higher-income families and those with better-educated fathers reported better physical and emotional well-being. The study emphasizes the importance of designing technology-integrated learning environments that consider students' socio-economic backgrounds and emotional needs. It also suggests that educational institutions should implement strategies to ensure equitable access to technology and support systems that mitigate the negative effects of excessive screen time. The findings advocate for a balanced approach to TBL integration, where its positive impact on engagement is maximized, and its physical and emotional challenges are minimized.

Keywords: *Technology-Based Learning, Academic Engagement, Physical Well-being, Emotional Well-being, College Students*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of technology has significantly impacted various aspects of education, bringing both opportunities and challenges. As technology evolves, educational capabilities improve, enabling them to meet the needs of today's students. The use of technologies is becoming increasingly popular across different fields. Within higher education, TBL (technology-based learning) plays a crucial role in enhancing the teaching and learning process, promoting active learning, and fostering authentic collaboration. The integration of technology in education has heightened student engagement, expanded digital access to information, and redefined traditional learning methods.

Moreover, technology plays a crucial role in students' academic activities, intellectual development, and creative expression. TBL tools enhance students' critical thinking and transformative learning skills. However, the integration of educational technology is not a one-size-fits-all approach; it should be customized to meet the specific needs of academic institutions, the subjects being taught, the levels of students, and their literacy skills.

Using technology, specifically laptops and televisions in the classroom, along with various PowerPoint templates with animation effects, transitions, designs, pictures, and videos, readable font styles and sizes, and logically organized information, stimulates and enhances students' engagement, focus, and participation during class discussion, making it easier for them to understand and retain information. This positive feedback motivates the researcher to innovate further, explore additional options, and incorporate new and engaging animations and styles into the lessons.

The use of a television in the classroom is also essential for TBL, and its placement within the classroom is crucial, as it must be visible to all students during class discussions. The researcher's observations indicate that if a television is positioned near a window, glare may affect the presentation, making it difficult for some students to see clearly. This, in turn, could reduce students' participation and potentially impact their physical and emotional well-being.

Moreover, as observed by the researcher, it has been noted that reliance on technology during class discussions presents challenges, particularly when power interruptions occur. To address this, the researcher implements alternative activities that allow lessons to continue despite electrical disruptions. Although power outages in the city are typically announced a week in advance, the researcher prepares activities accordingly to ensure continuity in learning and minimize disruptions.

Traditional teaching and learning have evolved into technology-integrated education, for technology has many benefits, ranging from education to entertainment;

however, it also poses risks when it comes to excessive usage. Spending long hours with technology is not good for one's health, (Unnisa, 2021) which is the process of the study, the negative effects of excessive use of technology, and the impact of technology-based learning on the physical health of college students.

Technology can be an appealing learning tool that enhances students' sense of connection and motivation. However, poorly designed TBL may induce stress and anxiety, thereby affecting their emotional well-being. Hence, the study also looks into students' range of emotions and feelings while engaging in learning integrated with technology. As cited by Koslouski et al. (2020), emotional well-being is complex, as it encompasses both the emotional quality of everyday experiences and judgments about life satisfaction and purpose. These features occur in the context of culture, life circumstances, resources, and life course. Nonetheless, the researcher focuses solely on students' emotions and feelings.

Research Questions

This research aimed to identify the impact of technology-based learning on the college students' academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being. This study specifically addressed the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Academic program
 - c. Parents' income
 - d. Parents' educational attainment
2. How do the students perceive the use of technology in learning?
3. Do the students significantly differ in their perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning when grouped according to their profile?
4. What is the impact of technology-based learning on students in terms of:
 - a. academic engagement
 - b. physical well-being
 - c. emotional well-being
5. Is there a significant difference in the impact of technology-based learning on students' academic engagement, physical and emotional well-being when grouped according to their profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the students' perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning and the perceived impact of technology-based learning on the students' academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive method, as defined by Fraenkel et al. (2012), the descriptive method is a method that aims to provide an accurate and systematic portrayal of the characteristics of a situation, population, or phenomenon that is used to various methods, including surveys, interviews, observations, and document analysis, to gather information. While the descriptive method often involves quantitative data, Creswell (2014) acknowledges the role of qualitative data, showing how qualitative and quantitative data can be used together to provide a more complete understanding of a research problem.

The researcher chose this design to clarify the characteristics of these impacts through utilizing a survey questionnaire that was administered to students, which provides a thorough account, enabling the understanding and interpretation of the influence of TBL on students.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Saint Ferdinand College, Main Campus, specifically, in the College of Criminology and the College of Business Education. The departments are integral parts of the institution's commitment to providing quality education, known for its strong Catholic foundation and commitment to academic excellence, which has grown into a reputable institution in the region. Further, the institution not only provides the aforementioned programs but also offers a variety of academic programs, including BS Accountancy, BS Nursing, BS Information Technology, BS Psychology, BS Education, and AB Political Science, and features numerous facilities that promote academic inquiry and community engagement.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The selected respondents consisted of 257 individuals who are first-year students from the COC (College of Criminology) and CBE (College of Business Education) departments, currently enrolled in their second semester in the school year 2024-2025. The researcher ensured that these respondents had access to technological devices for learning both within and outside the technology-integrated learning environment. The table below presents the number of students from each department.

Table 1
The Total Number of Respondents

Subject	Department	Number of Students
Purposive Communication	COC	53
	CBE	54
Philippine Literature	COC	109
Vocation and Teen Sexuality	COC	41

Total	257
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Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured approval from the school administration through a letter to administer the study's questionnaire. The researcher digitally administered survey questionnaires using Google Forms. The form was sent through the group communication platform. The survey was answered only during the researcher's class. To gauge the responses, the researcher collated, tabulated, and analyzed the data by downloading and generating it directly from Google Forms.

To identify and assess the perceptions and the impact of TBL on the academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being of the respondents concerning the integration of technology in learning, the researcher digitally administered the 77-item adapted and modified questionnaire. The respondents provided their feedback on the questionnaire items using a 4-point interval and a 4-point Likert scale response format.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To assess the impact of technology-based learning on students' academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being, and to explore their interrelationships, the researcher employed the following instruments: Frequency and percentage analyses were used to examine the respondents' profiles. The weighted mean was applied in analyzing students' perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning and the impact of TBL on students' academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being. A one-way ANOVA was utilized to analyze differences in students' perceptions of the use of technology in learning and the impact of TBL on their academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being when they are grouped according to profile, and Pearson's r test was employed in assessing the relationship between variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	149	57.98
Female	108	42.02
Total	257	100.0

Table 2 shows that out of 318 respondents, 257 students responded to the survey. 149 males constituted 57.98 percent of the population, and 108 females constituted 42.02

percent. Given that most of the respondents in this study are Criminology students, the observed gender distribution reflects a predominantly male population.

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Academic Program

Academic Program	Frequency	Percentage
College of Criminology	203	78.99
College of Business Education	54	21.01
Total	257	100

Table 3 shows that of the 257 respondents, 78.99 percent were from the College of Criminology, while 21.01 percent, comprising 54 students, were from the College of Business Education (Major in Marketing Management, Financial Management, Business Administration, and Hospitality Management).

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Parents' Income

Parents' Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below PHP 10,000	128	49.81
PHP 10,000 - PHP 20,000	64	24.90
PHP 20,000 - PHP 30,000	42	16.34
PHP 30,000 - PHP 50,000	13	5.06
Above PHP 50,000	10	3.89

Table 4 reveals that 49.81 percent of the respondents, comprising 128, have parents earning below PHP 10,000, followed by 64 respondents with 24.90 percent falling within the range of PHP 10,000 to PHP 20,000 family income. Additionally, 16.34 percent of the respondents, comprising 42, have parents earning between PHP 20,000 and PHP 30,000, while 5.06 percent, comprising 13 respondents, fall within the range of PHP 30,000 to PHP 50,000, and the smallest, 3.89 percent of the respondents have parents earning above PHP 50,000.

The findings depict that despite the financial constraints of most of the respondents' parents' monthly income, they are still able to enroll and pursue their courses in a private institution. According to the Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES), (PSA, 2025) which gathers data on family income and expenditure, including education, a household earning below PHP 10,000 is classified as poor by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA). Such households often struggle to meet their basic needs. Allocating a significant portion of this limited income toward private educational institutions for their children would impose financial constraints, which would limit them from affording necessities.

Parents' income is one of the most important factors for providing learning materials and resources for students. Thus, the implementation of RA 10931, the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act (UAQTE), (Ortiz et al., 2019) aims to provide all Filipinos with equal opportunity to quality tertiary education in both private and public educational institutions, and the implementation of RA 10648, *Iskolar ng Bayan* Act of 2014, (Republic of the Philippines, 2014) encouraging LGUs to create their scholarship program, establishing and maintaining a financial assistance system that shall be available to deserving students, especially the underprivileged. Thus, these policies have supported low-income families to enable their children to pursue tertiary education.

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Parents' Educational Attainment

Parents' Educational Attainment	Frequency (Father)	Percentage	Frequency (Mother)	Percentage
No formal education	5	1.95	1	0.39
Elementary undergraduate	36	14.01	31	12.06
Elementary graduate	39	15.18	25	9.73
High school undergraduate	32	12.45	28	10.89
High school graduate	54	21.01	83	32.30
Vocational/Technical course	5	1.95	1	0.39
College undergraduate	39	15.18	30	11.67
College graduate	46	17.90	58	22.57
Postgraduate degree	1	0.39	0	0.00

Table 5 presents data indicating that most parents have completed high school education, with 32.30 percent of mothers and 21.01 percent of fathers, followed by college education, with 22.57 percent of mothers and 17.90 percent of fathers. In contrast, only 0.39 percent of fathers earned a postgraduate degree, while none of the mothers were recorded in this classification.

The data suggest that while many parents possess foundational academic experience, few have pursued higher education. This educational profile may limit their ability to support students in tech-based learning environments, particularly in guiding digital tasks or showing autonomous learning.

According to the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework (Arbaugh et al., 2008), limited parental education and digital exposure may constrain teaching presence at home. However, well-designed technology platforms with clear instructions can mitigate these gaps by enhancing students' cognitive engagement and fostering self-directed learning. Additionally, Davis-Kean (2020) asserted that parental education shapes occupation and income, indirectly supporting children's academic success through expectations and cognitive stimulation.

2. How do the students perceive the use of technology in learning?

Table 6
Mean Score of the Respondents' Positive Perceptions on the Use of Technology in Learning

Items	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description
1. Learning through technology-based learning makes learning easy.	2.96	Agree
2. Integrating technology in class enables one to learn at one's own pace.	2.84	Agree
3. Integrating technology in class helps in the application of learning.	3.02	Agree
4. Integrating technology in class improves learning performance.	3.00	Agree
5. Integrating technology in class makes it easier for students to learn.	2.92	Agree
6. Integrating technology in class has a positive influence on students' learning.	2.94	Agree
7. Integrating technology in class is fun and engaging.	2.95	Agree
8. Integrating technology makes it easy for students to collaborate with others.	3.01	Agree
9. Integrating technology helps students improve their ability to communicate.	3.04	Agree
10. Integrating technology in class makes learning enjoyable and interactive.	2.90	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.96	Agree

The findings from Table 6 present the perception of the respondents on the use of technology in learning. It shows that the weighted mean score of 2.96 which falls within the range of "Agree," reveal the overall positive perceptions on the integration of technology in the learning process, emphasizing its significance among the respondents in improving communication skills, obtaining the highest mean score of 3.04; in applying acquired knowledge, with a mean score of 3.02; and in enabling learning collaboration, having a mean score of 3.01. Furthermore, the respondents agree with all the items. This indicates that respondents perceive technology integration positively, viewing it as a tool that facilitates and enhances learning. Serhan (2009) also found that technology builds student confidence, improving their ability to apply knowledge, which supports the researcher's findings.

However, the findings also reveal that item 2, "Integrating technology in class enables one to learn at one's own pace," obtained the lowest mean score of 2.84, though it still falls within the "Agree" range. This means that while students agree that technology helps them learn at their own pace, their level of agreement is not very strong. This could suggest that they do not often get the chance to learn independently when using technology in their current classroom setting.

This differs from Lowther et al.'s (2008) who argue that effective technology integration in education requires students' autonomy, capability, and creativity. They

emphasized that autonomy allows students to control their learning through ICT, then they become capable of working effectively alone and with others, and creativity is fostered through collaborative learning, which builds new knowledge.

Table 7
Mean Score of the Respondents' Negative Perceptions on the Use of Technology in Learning

Items	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description
11. Technology integration hinders students from focusing on their strengths, exploring their interests, and improving weak areas.	2.73	Agree
12. Integrating technology in the teaching-learning process makes it difficult to become skilled.	2.71	Agree
13. Integrating technology in class prevents students from accomplishing tasks effectively.	2.70	Agree
14. Integrating technology in class decreases students' productivity.	2.51	Agree
15. Integrating technology in class is not useful for learning.	2.22	Disagree
16. Integrating technology in class makes learning less interesting.	2.49	Disagree
17. Integrating technology in class is a distraction.	2.39	Disagree
18. Integrating technology restrains students from accessing high-quality and current information.	2.86	Agree
19. Integrating technology does not improve students' critical thinking.	2.37	Disagree
20. Integrating technology only makes things more confusing.	2.51	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.55	Agree

The data in Table 7 indicate the respondents' negative perceptions toward technology integration in learning. The weighted mean score of 2.55, which falls within the range of "Agree," indicates that most of the respondents negatively perceived technology integration in learning, and reveals that TBL restricts students to quality and current information, with the highest mean score of 2.86. This implies that students may feel that TBL makes them just receive information instead of actively participating, which can lead to frustration. This could also reflect institutional gaps, such as limited internet access, lack of adequate tools or materials, limiting student access to needed resources. Ghavifekr et al.'s (2016) study shows that a lack of access and tech support can limit information quality, which validates the findings of this study.

In contrast, the lowest mean score of 2.22 indicates that most respondents do not view technology integration as unhelpful to learning. The findings imply that respondents still recognize technology as helpful for their academic engagement and achievement.

3. Do the students significantly differ in their perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning when grouped according to their profile?

Table 8
Results of the test of significant difference in the perceptions of the students regarding the use of technology in learning when grouped according to profile

Profile	Perceptions	P - value	Level of significance	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	Positive	0.772	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Negative	0.610	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Academic program	Positive	0.460	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Negative	0.268	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Parents' income	Positive	0.905	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Negative	0.009	0.05	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Father's Educational Attainment	Positive	0.236	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Negative	0.126	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Mother's Educational Attainment	Positive	0.523	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Negative	0.250	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

The independent t-test was applied to analyze differences in perceptions based on sex, while one-way ANOVA was used for academic programs and parents' income. Additionally, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed to assess differences in perceptions based on the father's and mother's educational attainment. All tests were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance.

The results indicate that the p-values for both positive and negative perceptions across sex, academic program, and parents' educational attainment are greater than 0.05, suggesting that there are no significant differences in students' perceptions of technology in learning based on these factors. This implies that, regardless of sex, academic program, or parents' education, students generally share similar perceptions, both positive and negative, toward the use of technology in learning. This means that access to digital platforms is not confined to individuals of high socioeconomic status or advanced educational attainment. Respondents showed that access to the internet, social media, and digital devices was common across all social and educational backgrounds, including those with limited financial resources or formal education. The results indicate

that technology has now become pervasive, offering equalizing access across diverse sectors of society.

However, the results differ when students are grouped according to parents' income. The p-value for positive perceptions is greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis, indicating no significant difference in students' positive perceptions based on their parents' income. In contrast, the p-value for negative perceptions is less than 0.05, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests a significant difference in the respondents' negative perceptions depending on their parents' income.

Based on the researcher's informal interview and observations to the respondents, it was found that respondents from higher-income households tend to focus more on social media, since they have better access to internet connectivity, but view technology primarily as a source of entertainment rather than as a tool for learning. This is evident from the computed weighted mean score of 2.64, as the highest in the respondents' negative perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning when grouped according to their parents' income.

Whereas respondents from lower-income households may face more challenges and barriers in accessing and utilizing technology for learning compared to their peers from mid-income families. This is evident from the computed weighted mean score of 2.62, second to the highest in the respondents' negative perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning when grouped according to their parents' income.

The findings contradict Erlich et al.'s study, (2013) which claimed that low-income students are least likely to have access to technology or use it for educational purposes at home. In contrast, the current data shows that most respondents report high levels of home access.

4. What is the impact of technology-based learning on students in terms of:

Table 9
The Mean Score of the Respondents' Answers on the Impact of TBL in terms of Academic Engagement (Behavioral Aspect)

Items	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description	Impact
1. Integrating technology in learning helps me to learn independently.	2.96	Agree	High Impact
2. I feel very satisfied when I learn new knowledge and skills through technology.	3.09	Agree	High Impact
3. I enjoy doing my best to learn skills through technology.	2.98	Agree	High Impact
4. Technology-based learning makes me want to practice more.	3.00	Agree	High Impact
5. Technology helps in accomplishing my project the correct way.	3.07	Agree	High Impact

6. Technology makes me put more effort into learning.	2.95	Agree	High Impact
7. Technology makes me keep trying even if something is hard.	3.00	Agree	High Impact
8. Technology makes me look forward to finishing my tasks successfully.	3.03	Agree	High Impact
9. Technology makes me feel excited when I am doing a given task.	2.87	Agree	High Impact
10. Technology increases my motivation for the subject.	2.83	Agree	High Impact
Weighted Mean	2.98	Agree	High Impact

Table 9 reflects the overall positive behavior on TBL, with a weighted mean of 2.98, which falls within the range of "Agree" or "High Impact." The majority of the respondents feel satisfaction when acquiring new knowledge and skills through TBL, with the highest mean score of 3.09, evident in item 2. This means that technology integration makes learning more enjoyable and fulfilling, fosters pride as they gain new knowledge and skills, and encourages active participation, allowing them to absorb information while enjoying the learning process.

While item 10, indicating that technology increases their motivation for the subject, gained the lowest mean score of 2.83, it still shows that technology plays an important role in motivating students to learn the subject. The score indicates that while some students may be less convinced, many still recognize that technology helps them stay interested and engaged. So, while it is not the top-rated factor, technology still has a positive influence on their motivation.

The findings correspond to Octavia and Hamilton-Hankins (2017), who observed that technology enhances students' engagement and increases motivation in their learning, and that students expressed enjoyment and enthusiasm when using technology for learning activities.

Table 10
The Mean Score of the Respondents' Answers on the Impact of TBL in terms of Academic Engagement (Social Aspect)

Items	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description	Impact
1. Technology integration makes me try to work with others who can help me.	2.98	Agree	High Impact
2. Technology integration increases my motivation towards collaboration.	2.86	Agree	High Impact
3. Integrating technology is important for interacting with other groups.	3.00	Agree	High Impact
4. Technology improves my participation and engagement.	2.98	Agree	High Impact
5. Class discussions with technology integration help me to develop a sense of collaboration.	2.93	Agree	High Impact

6. I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by others.	2.85	Agree	High Impact
7. Getting to know others gave me a sense of belonging in the class.	2.96	Agree	High Impact
8. Technology-based learning communication is an excellent medium for social interaction.	2.94	Agree	High Impact
9. I felt comfortable conversing through Technology-based learning.	2.83	Agree	High Impact
10. I felt comfortable interacting with other course participants.	2.83	Agree	High Impact
Weighted Mean	2.92	Agree	High Impact

The data indicate that respondents generally perceive TBL as having a positive impact on academic engagement in terms of the social aspect. All items show mean scores falling within the range of "Agree," demonstrating a strong impact on the respondents, with the weighted mean of 2.92 highlighting this overall positive impact. The highest mean score of 3.00, obtained from item 3, "Integrating technology is important for interacting with other groups," indicates that TBL significantly facilitates interaction with other groups. While items 9 and 10, which reflect students' comfort in conversing through technology-based learning and interacting with other participants, obtained the lowest mean scores of 2.83. Despite the lower mean scores, the results still reflect a significant impact, suggesting that TBL contributed to students' comfort in engaging with others. These findings reveal that the integration of TBL enhances student participation, collaboration, and interaction. These results affirm respondents' positive perceptions of TBL, as shown in Table 7, item 9, "Integrating technology helps students improve their ability to communicate," which obtained the highest mean score and demonstrates its contribution to the development of students' communication skills.

The findings align with Bhat's study, which states that technology also enables collaboration among students, both within the classroom and across distances, providing platforms for students to work together on projects, share ideas, and learn from their peers. Furthermore, the general positive impact of TBL on students' social engagement aligns with Monserate's (2018) study, which also emphasized the role of technology in fostering collaboration among students.

Table 11
The Mean Score of the Respondents' Answers on the Impact of TBL in terms of Academic Engagement (Cognitive Aspect)

Items	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description	Impact
1. Integrating technology in learning helps me improve my technological skills.	2.98	Agree	High Impact
2. Technology makes me try to understand my mistakes when I get something wrong.	2.91	Agree	High Impact
3. Integrating technology in learning makes it very important to accomplish tasks.	2.95	Agree	High Impact
4. Technology helps in developing the learning process.	3.02	Agree	High Impact

5. Course activities piqued my curiosity.	2.84	Agree	High Impact
6. I felt motivated to explore content-related questions.	2.97	Agree	High Impact
7. I utilized a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course.	2.93	Agree	High Impact
8. Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me resolve content-related questions.	3.04	Agree	High Impact
9. Technology-based discussions were valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.	2.86	Agree	High Impact
10. Technology-based learning activities helped me construct explanations and solutions.	2.96	Agree	High Impact
Weighted Mean	2.95	Agree	High Impact

The data indicate that respondents generally view TBL as having a positive impact on academic engagement in terms of the cognitive aspect. All items yielded mean scores within the "Agree" range, indicating a high level of impact, with the weighted mean of 2.95 highlighting this overall positive impact. The highest mean score of 3.04 from item 8, "Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me resolve content-related questions," demonstrates that TBL significantly enhances students' ability to address content-related questions through brainstorming. This suggests that respondents benefit from tasks that encourage exploration and critical thinking, as well as from solving content-related problems through meaningful activities. Hence, tasks requiring analysis appear to be strengthened through TBL.

On the other hand, item 5 indicates that course activities piqued respondents' curiosity, earning the lowest mean score of 2.84, yet still showing a high level of impact. This suggests that while curiosity was less dominant compared to other outcomes measured, it remains relevant in cognitive engagement fostered by TBL. The score may reflect differences in how curiosity is stimulated, depending on learners' prior knowledge and interests.

This general positive impact on cognitive engagement is supported by Friedman and Coates' (2009) study, which states that ICTs enhance engagement through knowledge and skills development. Specifically, the finding that TBL enhances brainstorming and exploration aligns with Jonassen's (2000) concept of mind tools, which emphasizes the role of technology in facilitating critical thinking and knowledge construction. Mind tools are designed to extend learners' cognitive functioning by engaging them in meaningful operations during the learning process. Rather than reproducing information, learners using cognitive tools actively construct knowledge and develop critical thinking skills.

Table 12
Respondents' Answers on the Impact of TBL in terms of Physical Well-being

Attribute	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description	Impact
1. I suffer from headaches when using technology in class.	2.39	Rarely	Low Impact
2. My eyes hurt when using digital devices in class.	2.37	Rarely	Low Impact
3. My vision is affected by screen time during lessons.	2.32	Rarely	Low Impact
4. I get constipated from sitting a lot in tech-based classes.	2.19	Rarely	Low Impact
5. My neck hurts because of using technology in class.	2.17	Rarely	Low Impact
6. I have gained weight from less activity in tech-integrated classes.	2.10	Rarely	Low Impact
7. My hands or wrists hurt when typing and using digital devices in class.	2.14	Rarely	Low Impact
8. My back hurts from sitting for too long in tech-based lessons.	2.39	Rarely	Low Impact
9. I experience body pain from using technology in class.	2.12	Rarely	Low Impact
10. I feel exhausted when using technology during lessons.	2.19	Rarely	Low Impact
11. I have lost my appetite due to stress from using technology in class.	2.15	Rarely	Low Impact
12. I have trouble sleeping from too much screen exposure during class.	2.27	Rarely	Low Impact
Weighted Mean	2.24	Rarely	Low Impact

The data indicate that respondents rarely experience negative physical-related issues when TBL is integrated into the learning process, as reflected by a weighted mean of 2.24, classified within the "Rarely" range, as all indicators are, posing minimal negative physical impact, and minor discomfort. The most common concerns, though still infrequent, are headaches (Item 1) and back pain from prolonged sitting (Item 8), sharing a mean score of 2.39. The infrequent discomfort indicates that such issues are minor, manageable, and not significantly disruptive to the learning process. These results support that TBL is physically sustainable for most students.

This aligns with Unnisa's (2021) study, which highlights that prolonged technology use can lead to body pain and vision problems. Furthermore, Liu et al.'s (2023) findings noted that excessive screen time can cause back pain, supporting the observation of back pain from prolonged TBL use.

In contrast, item 6 earned the lowest mean score of 2.10, reflecting weight gain due to less activity in tech-integrated classes, making it the least frequent concern. This suggests that such instructional modes and approaches do not significantly affect

respondents' physical health. Moreover, they may not associate TBL with changes in physical weight, implying that the concern is neither noticeable nor perceived as relevant to their learning. This may instead reflect diverse lifestyle factors, such as routines outside the classroom, indicating that TBL integration alone is not viewed as a major contributor to sedentary behavior.

Table 13
Mean Score of the Respondents' Impact of TBL in terms of Emotional Well-being

Attribute	Computed Mean (\bar{x})	Description	Impact
1. I feel tired for no reason from using technology in learning.	2.21	Rarely	Low Impact
2. I feel nervous using technology in learning.	2.09	Rarely	Low Impact
3. Technology in education makes me feel hopeless.	2.05	Rarely	Low Impact
4. Technology-based learning makes me fidgety.	2.27	Rarely	Low Impact
5. I cannot sit still because of technology in class.	1.95	Rarely	Low Impact
6. Technology in learning frustrates me.	2.00	Rarely	Low Impact
7. I feel sad about tech-driven learning.	1.99	Rarely	Low Impact
8. I do not feel useful in tech-based learning.	1.97	Rarely	Low Impact
9. I feel like I am not reaching my potential in tech-integrated learning.	2.16	Rarely	Low Impact
10. I do not contribute much to tech-based learning.	2.06	Rarely	Low Impact
11. I feel afraid of using technology in learning.	2.12	Rarely	Low Impact
12. I feel insecure and uncertain with technology in learning.	2.06	Rarely	Low Impact
13. Tech-based learning makes me feel bored and unmotivated.	2.07	Rarely	Low Impact
Weighted Mean	2.08	Rarely	Low Impact

The weighted mean of 2.08 places all indicators within the “Rarely” range, indicating that respondents rarely experience negative emotional impact and challenges when TBL is integrated in the learning process. The predominant concerns, despite low occurrence, were fidgetiness and tiredness, as shown in items 4 and 1, with mean scores of 2.27 and 2.21, respectively.

The fact that respondents rarely experience emotional discomfort, such as fidgetiness and tiredness, validates their negative perceptions that TBL restricts information and hinders focus. Fidgety behaviors such as pen tapping or clicking, chair rocking, foot tapping, going in and out of the classroom, and seat shifting can fragment the attention of the student, making it harder to sustain focus, which can lead to diminished attention and may weaken retention of information during class. Moreover,

when fidgetiness heightens, students may overlook or miss instructional cues, spoken directions, or a slide page in a presentation that links to accessing information. These negative perceptions likely contribute to the negative emotional responses, implying a connection between perceived technological limitations and emotional well-being.

This is consistent with the study of Ibrahim et al. (2025). They also found that using educational technologies can negatively affect emotional well-being when it creates cognitive strain or disrupts focus. The findings highlighted that effective management of cognitive load can reduce these negative effects. Therefore, poorly managed technology integration harms student well-being and learning outcomes.

Moreover, Ruci et al. (2009), showed that emotions directly shape cognition, with individuals more likely to form false memories that align with their current mood. Negative emotions can distort attention, memory, and information processing, which also validates the current study, that emotional discomfort during technology-based learning fragments attention and weakens retention. Both suggest that negative emotions hinder cognitive performance.

5. Is there a significant difference in the impact of technology-based learning on students' academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being when grouped according to their profile?

Table 14
Results of the test of significant difference in the impact of technology-based learning on students' academic engagement when grouped according to profile

Profile	Academic engagement	P - value	Level of significance	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	Behavioral	0.270	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Social	0.338	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Cognitive	0.671	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Academic program	Behavioral	0.386	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Social	0.340	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Cognitive	0.283	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Parents' income	Behavioral	0.670	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Social	0.275	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Cognitive	0.325	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

Father's Educational Attainment	Behavioral	0.091	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Social	0.539	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Cognitive	0.188	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Mother's Educational Attainment	Behavioral	0.961	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Social	0.712	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Cognitive	0.649	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

The results in Table 14 reveal that the p-values for sex and academic engagement—namely, behavioral, social, and cognitive engagement—are all greater than 0.05. Similar results are observed for the p-values associated with academic program, parents' income, and father's and mother's educational attainment in relation to academic engagement. To analyze these differences, an independent t-test was used to compare academic engagement based on sex, while a one-way ANOVA was applied to examine the differences in academic programs and parents' income. Additionally, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed to assess differences in academic engagement concerning the father's and mother's educational attainment. All tests were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance.

Since all p-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the researcher accepts the null hypothesis in all cases. This indicates that none of the profile variables has a significant impact on the behavioral, social, or cognitive engagement of students in technology-based learning. Furthermore, the academic engagement in technology-based learning appears to be independent of students' demographic and socioeconomic backgrounds. The educational attainment of parents, whether highly educated or economically disadvantaged, does not directly determine a student's academic engagement. Engagement in academic activities is intrinsically personal and primarily influenced by the student's own motivation and effort. Regardless of sex, socioeconomic status, and parental educational attainment, it is the student's individual disposition and motivation, and willingness to strive that drive academic involvement.

The findings contrast with prior research emphasizing demographic and socioeconomic influences on academic engagement. Korir et al. (2017) found that parental income significantly influences academic performance through access to learning resources. Similarly, Castillo et al. (2025) found that socioeconomic status strongly affects achievement amidst the digital divide. Whereas, the findings of this study revealed no significant effects of sex, program, parents' income, or parental education on behavioral, social, or cognitive engagement in technology-based learning among college students. This suggests that while family background and socioeconomic status may matter in adolescent contexts or where access to technology is unequal, engagement in college-level technology-based learning is driven by individual motivation and effort.

Further, during the pandemic, TBL became common for all students, accessible to them regardless of sex or socioeconomic background. Most students became familiar with using technological and digital tools for learning. However, its impact on academic engagement appears limited. While students have adapted to technological learning tools, their personal motivation to engage in academic tasks has remained mostly unchanged.

Table 15
Results of the test of significant difference in the impact of technology-based learning on students' physical well-being when grouped according to profile

Profile	P value	Level of significance	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.175	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Academic program	0.864	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Parents' income	0.006	0.05	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Father's Educational Attainment	0.019	0.05	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Mother's Educational Attainment	0.271	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

The results indicate that the p-values for parents' income and father's educational attainment are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests a significant difference in students' physical well-being when grouped according to parents' income and father's educational attainment.

These findings imply that students' physical well-being in a technology-based learning environment significantly varies based on their parents' income and their father's educational attainment. Students from higher-income families may benefit from better access to comfortable study environments, healthier lifestyles, and improved healthcare, while those from lower-income backgrounds may experience greater physical strain due to less favorable study conditions. In essence, household resources may affect whether students have a comfortable place to study, enough food, and access to healthcare, all of which contribute to physical well-being.

Similarly, a father's higher educational attainment may be associated with greater awareness of health-related concerns and better support for their child's physical well-being, particularly in a technology-driven learning setting. A father's level of education may influence how the family values health, study habits, and support at home. These attitudes and beliefs may influence how students take care of themselves and cope with technology-based learning. The level of a father's education might affect the family's approach to health and learning. When fathers are more educated, they may encourage how a family thinks about health, promote positive study habits, and routines at home.

The same study found that parental income and parental education influence the physical activity and well-being of students, which supports the findings of this study. The findings of Ziegeldorf et al. (2024) showed that parental education and family health climate significantly shape children's physical activity, highlighting the influence of family background on well-being. It aligns with the study's findings that household resources and parental education shape students' physical well-being in tech-based learning environments.

The findings also reveal that there is no significant difference in the impact of technology-based learning on the physical well-being of the respondents when grouped according to sex, academic program, and mother's educational attainment. Thus, the researcher accepts the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level since the p-values are greater than 0.05. This indicates that regardless of whether students are male or female, enrolled in different academic programs, or have mothers with varying levels of education, their physical well-being in a technology-based learning environment remains relatively similar.

Table 16
Results of the test of significant difference in the impact of technology-based learning on students' emotional well-being when grouped according to profile

Profile	P value	Level of significance	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.324	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Academic program	0.142	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Parents' income	0.028	0.05	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Father's Educational Attainment	0.001	0.05	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Mother's Educational Attainment	0.448	0.05	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

The results indicate that the p-values for parents' income and father's educational attainment are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates a significant difference in students' emotional well-being when grouped according to parents' income and father's educational attainment. It implies that students from different income brackets and paternal educational backgrounds experience distinct emotional challenges and supports. Financial stability can improve students' access to technology, study spaces, and emotional support, making it easier for them to adjust to tech-based learning. Hence, students' emotional well-being depends not just on personal strength but also on the support systems around them.

According to the researcher's informal interview and observation, students from higher-income families or more educated fathers often feel less stressed and more confident because they have better access to technology and helpful support at home. In

contrast, students from low-income or less-educated paternal backgrounds, often linked to poor digital access, may face more emotional stress, school pressure, and limited parental academic support.

In support of the study’s findings, Gandarillas et al. (2024) concluded that family factors significantly moderate the impact of digital technologies on university students’ mental health. They found that a stable family environment—marked by higher parental education and income—acts as a protective factor against anxiety and irritability linked to digital immersion. The study emphasized that family factors are inseparable from students’ ability to manage the demands of technology-based education, with socioeconomic and educational stability leading to more positive emotional outcomes. These evidences confirm that variations in emotional well-being in technology-based learning reflect differences in parental income and backgrounds.

On the other hand, the researcher accepts the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance for sex, academic program, and mother’s educational attainment. Thus, there is no significant difference in the emotional well-being of the respondents in a technology-based learning environment. This suggests that regardless of students’ sex, academic program, or mothers’ educational attainment, their emotional well-being in a technology-based learning environment remains relatively similar. It implies that students appear to adapt emotionally to tech-based learning in similar ways, regardless of these demographic factors.

These findings suggest that technology in education has become pervasive and accessible to many students, regardless of their sex or academic program. It also shows that emotional well-being in tech-based learning is more about family circumstances, such as income and a father’s education, than personal traits or a mother’s education.

6. Is there a significant relationship between the students’ perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning and the perceived impact of technology-based learning on the students’ academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being?

Table 17
Results of the significant relationship between the students’ perceptions regarding the use of technology in learning and the perceived impact of TBL on students’ academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being

Variables	Computed value of r (relationship)	P-value	Level of significance	Analysis	Decision	Impact
Positive perceptions and behavioral engagement	0.628	P < 0.001	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Positive perceptions and social engagement	0.658	P < 0.001	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Positive perceptions and cognitive engagement	0.625	P < 0.001	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Positive perceptions and physical well-being	0.003	P = 0.964	0.05	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
Positive perceptions and emotional well-being	- 0.077	P = 0.220	0.05	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
Negative perceptions and behavioral engagement	0.089	P = 0.157	0.05	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
Negative perceptions and social engagement	0.179	P = 0.004	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Negative perceptions and cognitive engagement	0.127	P = 0.043	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Negative perceptions and physical well-being	0.240	P < 0.001	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Negative perceptions and emotional well-being	0.409	P < 0.001	0.05	p < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results reveal that the p-values for positive perceptions and behavioral, social, and cognitive engagement, as well as for negative perceptions and social engagement, cognitive engagement, physical well-being, and emotional well-being, are all less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there are significant relationships between positive perceptions and behavioral, social, and cognitive engagement, while negative perceptions were significantly related to social and cognitive engagement, as well as physical and emotional well-being.

The findings indicate that positive perceptions of technology in learning exhibit a moderate to strong positive correlation with students' academic engagement. This suggests that students with positive perceptions of technology use tend to participate more actively and engage deeply in their learning. This correlation implies that positive perceptions toward TBL may enhance motivation, participation, and effort in learning tasks.

Although negative perceptions of technology show weak correlations with academic engagement and physical well-being, these perceptions remain relevant. It suggests that students who dislike TBL may not entirely disengage or experience physical

discomfort; hence, their negative views and mild discomfort with TBL could still influence how they engage and feel physically.

On the other hand, the correlation between negative perceptions of technology and emotional well-being is moderate. This means students who are skeptical of TBL may be more likely to be emotionally affected. Their negative views could manifest as frustration, anxiety, uncertainty, fear, and other emotional discomforts with technological tools.

In contrast, Table 14 also reveals no significant relationship between positive perceptions of technology and students' physical and emotional well-being, as well as negative perceptions of technology and behavioral engagement. The correlation between positive perceptions of technology and physical and emotional well-being is very weak to negative. This implies that even students who enjoy using technology may still experience physical and emotional discomfort. Given that the indicators of physical and emotional well-being reflect negative experiences, this finding reveals that liking technology does not protect students from the downsides of using it.

The findings of this study strongly validate the findings of Cantoria et al. (2004), examined the effects of technology integration on student engagement. Their study found strong correlations between technology use and behavioral and cognitive engagement, showing that digital tools can significantly enhance participation and learning outcomes. Similarly, this study revealed significant relationships between positive perceptions of technology and students' behavioral, social, and cognitive engagement, yet no significant relationship with physical or emotional well-being. Thus, both concluded that students with positive attitudes toward technology tend to demonstrate greater participation, collaboration, and cognitive engagement in their learning.

Conclusions

The researcher's analysis of the data led to the conclusion that technology-based learning has a positive impact on students' academic engagement across three key aspects: behaviorally, socially, and cognitively. Its impact enhances motivation and satisfaction in learning, promotes interaction, collaboration, and increased engagement with peers, and enriches brainstorming and the learning process.

Moreover, technology-based learning integration also impacts the physical and emotional well-being of the students. Students experience minimal physical and emotional discomfort, such as headaches, back pain from prolonged sitting, fidgetiness, and tiredness, which validates their negative perceptions of technology-based learning, suggesting a connection between perceived technological constraints and emotional well-being.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are presented based on the findings and conclusions of this study:

1. To address existing disparities, educational institutions and administrators must implement programs to bridge the disparities in technology, which include providing students from disadvantaged backgrounds with technical support and internet connectivity.
2. To promote interaction and focus while minimizing potential physical and emotional strain, curriculum planners are encouraged to adapt to emerging trends and design technology-enhanced activities that support academic engagement while ensuring healthy screen use and emotional care; and integrate technology-based learning with pluralized strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles and students' needs, especially those whose well-being is affected by family income and education.
3. To sustain comprehensive and accessible educational materials, educational technology developers are encouraged to develop platforms that enhance academic engagement and support student well-being. This includes interactive features, distraction management, screen time control, emotional feedback and check-ins, and adaptive designs for diverse learners, including those affected by socioeconomic and parental education factors.
4. Since the impact of technology-based learning on the academic engagement of the students is highly positive, to sustain the positive effects, it is recommended that teachers should adopt a balanced approach in integrating technology in the teaching and learning process, to carefully select and integrate technologies that enhance learning, and mitigate potential disadvantages. Moreover, to tailor technology-based learning to students' needs and preferences, teachers are also encouraged to incorporate students' feedback and insights into their integration strategies, thereby enhancing student engagement, motivation, participation, learning outcomes, and addressing technological disparities and physical and emotional discomfort.
5. Given the minimal negative impact of technology-based learning on students' physical and emotional well-being, teachers are still encouraged to integrate strategies into the learning process to promote, support, and nurture the students' well-being within the technology-based learning environment by providing emotional and physical support, such as: providing adjustable workstations, varying learning activities, incorporating engaging learning activities, initiating mood assessment, and normalizing tech glitches to establish positive and supportive technology-based learning for the students.
6. Considering the relatively minimal impact of technology-based learning on students' emotional well-being, it is recommended that guidance counselors

implement systematic and continuous monitoring of students' well-being. This will enable early detection of emotional challenges and facilitate timely, targeted interventions. Moreover, counselors should enhance and diversify support programs that foster resilience, teach adaptive coping mechanisms, and encourage responsible and balanced use of technology. Collaborative efforts with educators and parents can further amplify these efforts, ensuring a comprehensive framework for student well-being in tech-integrated learning environments.

7. Due to differences in family income and a father's level of education, households vary in how they support health, learning, and overall student well-being. All parents—regardless of socioeconomic status—should be encouraged to create supportive home environments, promote positive study routines, and ensure access to basic health needs. Moreover, the educational attainment of fathers has been shown to shape family attitudes toward learning and emotional well-being. Therefore, it is recommended that parents actively support their children in managing academic, physical, and emotional challenges.
8. Schools and community stakeholders may also consider implementing parent-focused programs that raise awareness and equip parents to better support their children's well-being, navigate tech tools, and build a supportive home environment, helping bridge gaps across diverse family backgrounds.
9. Due to the highly beneficial effect of technology integration on student learning, future researchers may explore the potential long-term effects of technology-based learning on the students' academic engagement, physical, and emotional well-being, specifically, the challenges of integrating technology into the learning process and its impact on lower-income families.
10. With the observed positive growth in student academic engagement through technology-based learning, it is recommended that future studies explore more on the role of the teacher in the successful integration of technology into the teaching and learning process to effectively use technology in the classroom.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adheres to ethical guidelines and principles to ensure the integrity and welfare of all participants involved. The study followed the ethical standards set by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Saint Ferdinand College, City of Ilagan. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. The privacy and confidentiality of the respondents' information were strictly maintained, and data were anonymized before analysis to prevent identification of individual participants. Furthermore, the study ensured that no harm, either physical or emotional, was caused to the participants. The researchers also took necessary precautions to address any potential discomfort arising from the use of technology during the study, particularly its impact on the participants' physical and emotional well-being. All participants were given the option to ask questions and express concerns regarding the

study before and after their participation. The findings were reported with transparency and objectivity, maintaining the highest standard of research ethics.

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